

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS, PROBLEMS, PROPOSALS AND SOLUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7556254>

Abstract: This article covers the great importance given to modern methods of teaching foreign languages in the process of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the modern teaching methods necessary for learning them.

Key words: foreign language in preschool education, Finnish teaching system, method of signs and pictures.

Introduction. The spiritual development of the society depends on the content, form and essence of the educational work carried out in it. For this reason, there is a need to pedagogically interpret the renewal of education, the step-by-step education system implemented in our republic, and ensure the effective passage of this process. As our first president Islam Karimov said, "Currently, teaching foreign languages is given great importance in our country. This is certainly not for nothing. Today, there is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take their rightful place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners.

As we all know, the age of children in preschool education organizations is between 5-7 years old. And it is during this period that they develop rapidly both physically, mentally and emotionally, and the development of their intellectual potential begins at the first stage. Pre-school educational organizations provide an opportunity for the child to become a healthy and well-rounded person, to develop a passion for learning, to receive regular education 5 days a week, and to learn foreign languages. It is known that teaching foreign languages in our country has been defined as one of the important tasks since the first years of our independence.

This list of teaching strategies for the preschool classroom provides excellent transition opportunities to grow and learn as a teacher.

1. Method of working with characters and pictures.

One way to promote everyday vocabulary is to "have children verbally label common brands and symbols," says Dr. Elaine Fogel Schneider, director of Touchtime International. He explains that picture-to-word translation helps with language development. That is, it greatly helps children to learn new languages quickly and easily.

2. Voice recognition and matching method.

For this activity, you will need several large letters cut out of cardboard and several small, but not too large, things that begin with these letters. For example, if your letters are M and K, and you have a cat and an elephant. Begin by telling the child the sound a cat makes. Then, encourage the child to find something that starts with the same sound and stick it to the letter. Decorated letters can be kept in the classroom or taken home to share with parents. Schneider said the activity is a favorite among students because it gives them hands-on experience in learning. In addition, it creates a "masterpiece".

3. A way to get used to the natural world.

Children are very interested in learning lessons in the natural environment. Usually, a backyard garden can be a great way to educate them about the natural world. This method of growing a plant from seed to maturity is important not only for children to learn about their growth, but also for them to quickly and easily learn words in a foreign language. This method relieves stress and also helps to improve fine motor skills.

4. The method of adapting one's activity to students.

It can be easy to fall back on the teacher's manual or regular lessons you memorized in kindergarten. However, for some children, this causes problems. Gretzinger says children need to be sensitive to children in non-traditional homes. Think twice before asking students to draw pictures of their families - think about how an adopted or estranged child might feel and how other children might react need Inclusive activities can take a little longer, especially at the beginning of the year when you may not know all of your students, but a child's sense of embarrassment can be seen when you keep the mess. In this, the teacher should continue his creativity.

Pre-school education is the first stage of education and upbringing of our youth. The right preschool program should help our children grow and learn in ways that match their unique intelligence. But children, unlike adults, do not plan the future, tomorrow. The English lesson should be conducted in the sense of "here and now". Children learn a foreign language more easily by understanding stories or winning games. If they want, they can strengthen their organ information through games with their participation. On the one hand, the content expressed

in language should be related to children's life and daily life, on the other hand, activities or tasks that invite children to communicate should be interesting and important.

During the teaching of a foreign language, it is necessary to encourage each child to move. They should develop acoustic, kinesthetic, rhythmic and visual differentiation. Children are quick to organize, but quick to forget. Therefore, by repeating the speech several times, it is possible to help children remember it through games or handouts. Courses are spiral, and regular repetitions are an integral part. Successful foreign language teaching requires comprehensive methods. The quantity and quality of communication are the main reasons for faster language acquisition. During the lesson, students' attention should be focused mainly on the content and importance of the language. Students should first of all focus on the content of the language. The successful teaching of foreign languages also depends on how skillfully the teacher uses the opportunities available to him. Pupils should be given tasks so that they are forced to apply and retain their organic knowledge in the course of the lesson. Communication skills are important in the development of language skills. Social interaction, especially when students are able to apply the meaning of the language, enables them to use the language effectively. The teacher's ability to communicate and negotiate for this process is one of the main conditions for successful teaching.

Foreign language education, first of all, should encourage the organization of everyday, real knowledge and knowledge of a foreign language, but the development of specific knowledge should not be neglected. If we dwell on the methodical and didactic views used in the teaching of a foreign language, we must emphasize the following: The teaching process is not only communicative, but it is necessary to cover the competences that provide the ability to retain organic knowledge in the future. Many children are interested in learning foreign languages. Their interest is definitely related to the organization of the lesson process and the children's ability to achieve certain success in this lesson process. It is wrong to believe that this interest will remain the same throughout the years, therefore, pedagogues need to take care of it, that is, to ensure that the participants are happy and successful in the lesson. The content and purpose of the lesson will be understandable and memorable to the participants only if the topics being organized, as well as the questions, are important, interesting and relevant for the participants. Foreign language teachers encounter a different language and culture in foreign language education. For this reason, it is recommended to use reliable materials specific to the foreign language, texts and texts that can convey the culture of the country.

Today, when the English language teaching and learning system is improving in preschool educational institutions in Uzbekistan, one of the urgent issues is the development and introduction of technologies for the effective organization of English language teaching based on modern technologies and with the participation of interactive methods in the educational process. This scientific research is aimed at improving the educational system, increasing the effectiveness of teaching English through didactic games and advanced pedagogical technologies. The results of theoretical and experimental research conducted in order to ensure these processes made it possible to draw the following conclusions:

- along with a number of documents and decisions on education, literature related to several fields was reviewed. At the same time, the works and scientific articles of Uzbek scientists and foreign pedagogues focused on the actual issues of effective teaching of foreign languages to young children were analyzed and their positive opinions were used;

- for the purpose of didactic design of English lessons in pre-school educational organizations, the theoretical and practical foundations of teaching English with the help of didactic games, modern interactive methods, innovative technologies and ICT tools were studied and analyzed;

- English classes in pre-school educational institutions were observed, methodical recommendations were developed, sample lesson plans related to the topics were drawn up, experiment-tested and applied to the educational process;

- technology tools suitable for the purpose of the research were selected and applied to the English language teaching process.

Thus, the selection of didactic and computer game types suitable for the topic of English lessons, the uniqueness of the content of the material studied in the game technology and the consideration of the educational tasks, the game in the organization of the game activities of the students consideration of the structure has become a means of ensuring the effectiveness of the lesson.

It is advisable to work on the basis of the following recommendations when teaching English in preschool educational institutions:

- the purpose, content and style of English language training should be directed to the knowledge and requirements of the group of students;

- the training plan must correspond to the requirements, capabilities and needs of each child;

- English lessons should be connected with children's ideas about the world, and their abilities should be developed in other areas through game elements that are important for them.

Experts in the field of preschool education recommend not to rush to teach a child a foreign language from an early age. Approximately, in children up to 7 years of age, the right hemisphere of the head works. Therefore, logical thinking is still not well developed. All this prevents the child from conducting some training related to information analysis and logical thinking. That is why the classical way of teaching English to preschool children is not appropriate. That is, the way English is taught to adults (grammatical structures, etc.) is meant. Therefore, teaching English to children through games, that is, learning by playing, is effective.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the use of didactic games in English classes, it is desirable to have a system of didactic games with a content appropriate to the age of the children, their certain preparation and the subject.

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